

Minimising mathematical anxiety in teaching mathematics and assessing student's work

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This paper builds up a theoretical perspective and supports a possibility of creating a special assessment environment for students, where mathematical knowledge and understanding can be assessed with a reduced number of external psychological factors that may affect such assessment. A concept of a zone with minimal effect of anxiety is introduced and described. Students' successful work on extending the zone by means of a carefully selected chain of questions, where some questions only are part of a real assessment, allows students to reconsider their attitudes towards mathematics and assist teachers to identify some students' main learning difficulties as of psychological character. Further suggestions about developing and investigating special assessment environments are outlined and discussed.

Introduction

Assessment plays a central role in the teaching and learning of mathematics. However, a variety of factors can moderate successful learning of mathematical content before any kind of formal assessment takes place. Among others, they include anxiety in general terms, which often transforms into mathematical anxiety related specifically to the learning and studying of mathematics at school and university. Furthermore, it can affect assessment in the way where the actual results may not necessarily reflect the level of mathematical knowledge some students may possess (Stobart, 2008). The COVID-19 pandemic exposed this situation in multiple directions. While the total number of people in Australia affected by COVID-19 in one way or another can be seen as moderate in comparison with many other countries (e.g., many European countries and USA), anxiety among people in general and those studying mathematics in particular, has remained high in 2020. For the latter category of people, assessment risks connected with mathematical anxiety as the result of anxiety in society due to COVID-19 have also increased in 2020.

The paper presents a theoretical perspective on minimising mathematical anxiety in teaching mathematics and within assessment environments. Ashcraft, Krause, and Hopko (2007) define mathematical anxiety as the negative emotional reaction experienced by some individuals when put in situations that require mathematical reasoning or problem solving. These feelings can in turn affect mathematical performance. In particular, its assessment component. Reflecting on assessment's past outcomes and future perspectives Kilpatrick (1992) wrote:

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Today, E. L. Thorndike, the ardent positivist and trailblazing psychologist, almost seems justified in his faith; everything that exists can be measured – in some fashion. The 20th century has produced an assessment practice in education that is dominated the world over by psychometrics, the measurement of psyche. The challenge for the 21st century, as far as mathematics educators are concerned, is to produce an assessment practice that does more than measure a person's mind and then assign that mind a treatment. We need to understand how people, not apart from but embedded in their cultures, come to use mathematics in different social settings and how we can create a mathematics instruction that helps them use it better, more rewardingly, and more responsibly. (p. 43)

In this view, the development of assessment should address the progress of mathematics education as research and teaching domain. While sharing this point, but not having intentions for measuring one's mind or measuring mathematical anxiety, (e.g., Hopko, Mahadevan, Bare, and Hunt, 2003), the paper aims to build up theoretical foundations and methodological support for a possibility of creating a special assessment environment for mathematical works of students. An environment, where students' mathematical knowledge and understanding can be assessed with a reduced number of external psychological factors that may affect such assessment and compromise its validity and reliability. I am not claiming, to the least extent, that mathematical anxiety is something stable or unchanged and, for example, can be used as the best predictor of mathematical skills or mathematical abilities. I acknowledge instead that this is a socially developing symptom that can be recognised far beyond mathematics classrooms. Research based estimations give approximately 17% of the population that can be classified as high in mathematical anxiety (Ashcraft, Krause, & Hopko, 2007).

Theoretical perspective

My theoretical perspective is derived from constructivism, mathematical anxiety issues, and assessment methodology. I take into account that current learning perspectives incorporate three important assumptions (Anthony, 1996):

- Learning is a process of knowledge construction, not of knowledge recording or absorption.
- Learning is knowledge-dependent; people use current knowledge to construct new knowledge.
- The learner is aware of the processes of cognition and can control and regulate them.

From a constructivist perspective (von Glaserfeld, 1984), it is easier for a student, under appropriate arrangement of teaching, to act as an architect, to reveal the truth and construct new knowledge, than to learn ready-made knowledge without understanding its origin, meaning and interrelations (Davis, 1991). In other words, "learning is a process of construction in which the students themselves have to be the primary actors" (von Glaserfeld, 1984). Different forms of inquiry activities can help to minimise mathematical anxiety in teaching. One of the well-known forms of such activities is open problems. For open problems I follow Arsac, Germain and Mante (1988) characterisation which is based on the following:

- The statement of the problem is short, so that it can be easily understood, it fosters some discovery and all students are able to start the solution process.
- The statement of the problem does not suggest the method of solution, or the solution on itself, but it creates a situation stimulating the production of conjectures.
- The problem is set in a conceptual domain which students are familiar with.

Thus, students are able to master the situation rather quickly and get involved in attempts of conjecturing, planning solution paths and finding counter-examples in a reasonable time. I recognise, however, that a teacher is a person who has to regulate directions of students' work and adapt it to the lesson's needs. I also take into account that "the open problems promote the devolution of responsibility from the teacher to students" (Furinghetti and Paola, 2003, p. 399). For teacher's role to control any learning situation, Mercer's idea (1995) of "the sensitive, supportive intervention of a teacher in the progress of a learner, who is actively involved in some specific task, but who is not quite able to manage the task alone" helps to minimise mathematical anxiety (p. 74). Also, keeping a balance between students' collaborative and individual work is of great importance to address the issues of mathematical anxiety. It is also important, whenever possible, to make all efforts and find individual motivation for students to be successful in their studies.

Students with low achievement and learning difficulties in mathematics form a substantial part of all students. According to Magne (2003) "low achievement is a social construct. It is not a fact but a human interpretation of relations between the individual and his environment" (p. 9). Difficulties in learning mathematics are often seen through relationships between mathematical anxiety and mathematical competence (Hembree, 1990; Faust, Ashcraft & Fleck, 1996; Ma, 1999). Mathematical anxiety can vary from apprehension or dislike, worry to genuine fear or dread (McLeod, 1994) and includes more specific behavioural issues such as tension, frustration, helplessness, distress and mental disorganisation. Faust (1992) argued that mathematical anxiety fits the classic definition of a phobia. Miller and Bichsel (2004) pointed out that mathematical anxiety was the strongest predictor of mathematical performance. For example, Ashcraft, Kirk, and Hopko (1998) examined mathematical anxiety and mathematical competence in a study that administered a standardized mathematical achievement test. There are common regulations which allow students (in particular, students with special needs) to keep short breaks during the time tests/exams take place. Such regulations are designed to address difficulties some students may experience. However, the influence of anxiety during the assessment period cannot be resolved through such arrangements and needs to be investigated further.

I consider mathematical anxiety that affects students' performances in assessment items in connection with cognitive styles that coordinate functioning of cognitive processes (Gardner et al., 1959). According to Guilford (1980), cognitive styles can be characterised as intellectual organising functions that initiate and control psychological activity of the individual. The shift of the balance in the direction of uncontrolled cognitive styles brings to the activation of different components of mathematical anxiety whose significant

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accumulation within a short time interval leads to the blockage of those components of intellectual activity on the metacognitive level which are responsible for the creative regulation of the intellectual behaviour. As a result, students can demonstrate partial or full inability to work on questions from the assessment item. I distinguish three common situations that are classified according to the extent to which the students' work on assessment pieces can be affected.

- Student's performance is entirely affected by mathematical anxiety issues. Working on assessment questions represents sporadically made attempts with most of writing to be non-relevant to the assessment materials.
- Mathematical anxiety issues considerably affect student's performance. Although, it depends on particular assessment questions. Working on assessment questions represents a mixed type of work, where correct writing intertwines with non-relevant notes.
- Student's performance is marginally affected by mathematical anxiety issues, if it is affected at all.

As mentioned above, despite the low score students from the first two categories are likely to receive as their assessment result, the question about their knowledge of the corresponding mathematical content remains unanswered. One of possible directions is in developing a "free of anxiety" type of assessment environments, one of which is presented below.

I continue with a few definitions to describe in more detail the structure of the theoretical construction I have developed. I call *a zone with minimal effect of anxiety* the content knowledge that remains stably accessible by an individual having mathematical anxiety issues. Through a carefully selected chain of questions, this zone can be extended so that its extension will contribute to the gradual growth of confidence of that individual. The design of a chain of questions must have the following features:

- An increasing level of difficulty of questions with the final ones being equivalent to the level of difficulty of questions in standard assessment items. Some consecutive questions may be of approximately the same level of difficulty.
- There are no hints provided. Altogether, this is a set of connected or non-connected to each other tasks within a smaller topic that helps students to gain more confidence during their work on assessment items.
- Not all questions are subject to assessment. Students are provided with information about available marks for a whole piece of assessment or for groups of questions, not for the separate questions. Again, it aims to contribute to supporting students' confidence at the highest level possible.

Such sets of specially designed questions serve as a didactical tool that allows switching students' intellectual activity to an area where they can feel themselves comfortable up to a certain level. In special terms, it helps to unblock students' intellectual activity on the metacognitive level which improper functioning under the conditions of mathematical

anxiety may cause a significant decline in the results of students' assessment. The role of the principle of likes and dislikes, i.e., what I do well, I like to do it, in a competitive way, public way, under time constraints, etc., should not be underestimated in these circumstances. The presence of different questions from the same topic has a multiple meaning: firstly, it aims to bring students' attention to a constructivist point of view, where a number of questions from the same part of the course content may stimulate students' positive transition from the zone with minimal effect of anxiety to more challenging situations; secondly, it aims to divert students' attention from the anxiety issues since they (students) are no longer focussed on one particular question they may struggle with. However, they (anxiety issues) disperse on a number of questions instead, with some of them being perceived positively by students (in particular those within the zone with minimal effect of anxiety). Thus, minimising their possible negative influence.

Below I present an example of assessment material related to proof of the infinity of primes, which is suitable for discussion with Grade 11 and 12 students in Australia and first year undergraduate students. At first students are expected to work through the Erdős proof (provided to students) and then answer a number of questions on the topic. Full proof proposed by Erdős can be found, for example, in Aigner and Ziegler (2001). The special feature of this proof is that the construction leading to a contradiction is not the result of direct conclusions from the assumption and given conditions. This is a separate construction where the initial assumption and several implications from it are taken into account to find a way to come to a contradiction. Availability of easy-to-follow parts of the proof along with harder ones gives a "perfect landscape" in attempt to overcome psychological factors. Another feature of this example is a possibility to activate working memory – ability to hold a mental representation of information in mind while simultaneously engaged in other mental processes (Baddeley, 1986). Questions that represent the content beyond the lowest level of difficulty related to the topic (Q1) or accept analogical reproduction (Q3 and Q6) are not assessed. Questions Q1-Q3 form a zone with minimal effect of anxiety, while questions Q5, Q7 and Q9 appeal to working memory. Information in the brackets after each question is not available for students, i.e., students are not aware which questions are assessed and which are not.

Example: Questions for assessment (on the base of the Erdős proof of the infinity of primes)

1. What numbers are prime? Are all natural numbers prime? What can you say about 87? Is it prime? (Not assessed)
2. What is common between $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}$ and $\sum_{primes} \frac{1}{p}$? (Part of assessment)
3. What is the initial assumption of the Erdős proof? (Not assessed)
4. Can you explain in your own words what a convergent series is? Graphical representations can be used if required. (Part of assessment)

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5. When we select $\frac{1}{2}$ there must be a natural number k such that $\sum_{i \geq k+1} \frac{1}{p_i} < \frac{1}{2}$. Why do we choose $\frac{1}{2}$ here? What may happen if we replace $\frac{1}{2}$, say, with $\frac{1}{3}$? (Part of assessment)
6. What do the numbers N_b and N_s mean in the proof? (Not assessed)
7. N is listed as arbitrary in the proof. Why is the particular value $N = 2^{2k+2}$ important? How can we use it? (Part of assessment)
8. Describe in your own words how a proof scheme is built up in the Erdős proof. (Part of assessment)
9. Why can we represent every $n \leq N$ which has only small prime divisors in the form $n = a_n b_n^2$, where a_n is the square-free part? (Part of assessment)
10. Give some reasons why you think a contradiction can be achieved. (Part of assessment)

Concluding remarks

In this paper I have attempted to provide a theoretical background for teaching mathematics and creating a special assessment environment to address the needs of students with high levels of mathematical anxiety. The ideas discussed in the paper can be useful for the variety of mathematical topics studied in Grade 11 and 12 as well as at undergraduate level. They can be extended to lower school grades or used for extra curriculum activities where assessment is still in place. The concept of a zone with minimal effect of anxiety can be incorporated into different assessment methodology used for different categories of students (e.g., Black et al., 2003). The consequences of mathematical anxiety can be further specified and investigated to address specific components such as tension, frustration, helplessness, distress and mental disorganisation. Such specific behavioural issues do not form a unitary emotional scale or symptom and further investigation in this direction is required. This would allow obtaining a more complex picture in understanding how assessment can be organised in the most effective way with regard to specific behavioural issues. There is a possibility that some assessment results may remain low in the new assessment environment. In particular, if some students only answer those questions that are within the zone with minimal effect of anxiety. I would suggest interpreting such results as those that are still more reliable since they provide more information in comparison to standard assessment materials and may give more evidence that for some students their learning difficulties lie in the area of conceptual understanding of basic mathematical ideas rather than linked with mathematical anxiety. I would like to emphasize that the proposed theoretical model highlights the central role of a teacher as a representative and main facilitator of the “free of anxiety” environment in the classroom which is the main prerequisite for creating and supporting a “free of anxiety” assessment environment.

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